

Exchange Rate Dynamics and Nigeria's Export Competitiveness in the Global Market

Wokekoro, Ozulem Elvis PhD

¹Department of Economics

Rivers State University, Port Harcourt

Email: elvizwokz@gmail.com

Abstract

This study on Exchange Rate Dynamics and Nigeria's Export Competitiveness in the Global Market was conducted to analyze the impact of exchange rate volatility on Nigeria's exports, contributing to the ongoing debate on the interplay between exchange rate dynamics and trade performance. Annual time series data covering the period under review were collected on each of the variables employed in the model (EXP, EXR, INF and INT) from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin, 2023. EXR, INT and INF represented the exchange rate, interest rate and inflation rate were used as the independent variables while EXP, representing export was used as the dependent variable. The study conducted pre-estimation tests such as descriptive analysis and unit root test while post-estimation analysis included serial autocorrelation, heterokedasticity test, and CUSUM test. The study analyzed the data using the ECM ARDL regression model. It was found that exchange rate, inflation, and interest rate, have negative but significant relationship with EXP. The study concludes that exchange rate dynamics remain a critical determinant of Nigeria's competitiveness in the global market. It is recommended that the fiscal policies bothering on interest rate, inflation rate be amended to accommodate small scale manufacturers, giving them the opportunity to export more of their products.

Keywords: Export, inflation, interest rate, exchange rate, global market

Introduction

Exchange rates play a pivotal role in international trade, acting as a key determinant of a country's competitiveness in the global market according to Muoneke et al. (2022). For an economy like Nigeria, heavily reliant on crude oil exports and increasingly looking to diversify its export portfolio, the exchange rate's stability and alignment with global trends are critical (Duru et al., 2022). Over the years, Nigeria has experienced significant fluctuations in exchange rates due to varying economic policies, oil price volatility, and structural challenges (Shuabiu et al., 2021). These dynamics have far-reaching implications for the nation's export competitiveness in the global market (Nnoli et al., 2023).

Exchange rates are widely recognized as a key measure of an economy's international competitiveness and, by extension, its trade performance (Wang, 2015). The relationship between exchange rate volatility and exports has sparked extensive debate among governments, investors, researchers, and policymakers, particularly after the collapse of the Bretton Woods system of fixed

exchange rates in March 1973. Understanding this dynamic is vital for developing effective trade and exchange rate policies, as evidenced by a wealth of theoretical and empirical studies that offer conflicting conclusions (Ewubare et al., 2022).

Two main hypotheses dominate this discourse. The first suggests that exchange rate volatility negatively impacts trade flows. Proponents of this view, including Cushman (1983, 1986, 1988), Akhtar and Hilton (1984), and De Grauwe (1988), argue that uncertainty in exchange rates deters trade by increasing transaction risks and costs. On the other hand, a second hypothesis posits that exchange rate volatility can stimulate trade flows. Scholars such as Brada & Méndez (1988), Giovannini (1988), and Dellas & Zilberfarb (1993) suggest that volatility may create profit opportunities for risk-tolerant exporters and investors.

The negative effects of exchange rate volatility are often more pronounced in developing economies (Aghion & Howitt, 2007; Grier & Smallwood, 2007), where weaker financial systems limit the availability of hedging instruments. Furthermore, the impact is typically more significant under a flexible exchange rate regime, as noted by Olasehinde-Williams & Oshodi (2021). Long-term fluctuations in exchange rates also tend to have a greater influence on trade volumes than short-term variations, which can often be mitigated through cost-effective hedging mechanisms (Iheanachor & Ozegbe, 2021). However, even short-term volatility can disrupt trade by increasing risk premiums in forward exchange rates (Comfort, 2021).

For Nigeria, a country heavily dependent on crude oil exports as its main source of foreign exchange, these dynamics are especially pertinent (Ekanayake & Dissanayake, 2022). While the adoption of a floating exchange rate system after the Structural Adjustment Program (SAP) in 1986 aimed to stabilize the economy and boost exports, persistent exchange rate instability has limited the potential gains (Obomeghie & Ugbohmhe, 2021). Successive governments have implemented numerous measures, including the Second-tier Foreign Exchange Market (SFEM) and the Dutch Auction System (DAS), to stabilize the naira and enhance export performance (Sambo et al., 2021). Despite these efforts, Nigeria's export performance remains suboptimal, particularly in the non-oil sector, which is critical for sustainable economic growth and diversification (Mesagan et al., 2022).

The volatility of crude oil prices and the reliance on a single export commodity have exacerbated exchange rate fluctuations, highlighting the need for policies that stabilize the currency and promote non-oil exports (Osazevaru, 2021). Stable exchange rates would foster uninterrupted export activities, creating opportunities for economic growth, industrialization, and employment while maintaining external balance (Audi, 2024).

As Afolabi (2022) stated, every economy aspires to achieve vibrant and competitive international trade to accelerate economic growth and development. However, attaining this goal depends on the ability to expand and sustain the export of goods and services. With globalization, nations rarely operate in isolation; they engage in trade facilitated by the foreign exchange (forex) market (Orji et al., 2021). Nigeria, like many other countries, conducts transactions with various nations, requiring foreign currencies and exchange rates. CBN (2016) defines an exchange rate as the

current market price at which one national currency can be exchanged for another. Its importance lies in linking the price systems of two different countries, enabling a direct comparison of international transactions for goods and services (Uche & Nwamiri, 2022). Consequently, effective exchange rate management is essential for any developing country as it bridges domestic and global markets, reflects relative prices, and determines the country's competitiveness on the global stage (Williamson, 1994). To harness these benefits, monetary authorities implement policies that influence exchange rates. Changes in exchange rates ripple through the economy, affecting variables such as trade flows, interest rates, imports, exports, inflation, unemployment, and money supply (Oladipupo & Onotaniyohuwo, 2011).

A major theory in the discussion of exchange rate is the J-Curve theory which explains the relationship between exchange rates and trade flow. In the short term, currency depreciation often worsens the trade balance as higher import prices outweigh reduced import volumes. Over time, as demand becomes more price-sensitive, the trade balance improves, fulfilling the Marshall-Lerner condition. This condition asserts that currency depreciation will enhance a country's trade balance if the combined price elasticity of demand for exports and imports exceeds one (Abbas-Ali et al., 2014; Brown & Hogendorn, 2000).

As Isibor et al. (2022) observed, Nigeria previously implemented a fixed exchange rate system aimed at stabilizing the currency, controlling inflation, and making imports more affordable. However, this approach rendered exports non-competitive due to the naira's overvaluation, encouraged massive imports of finished goods, weakened domestic manufacturing, and exposed the currency to speculative attacks (Ibrahim et al., 2017). In 1986, Nigeria transitioned from a fixed exchange rate to a floating regime under the Structural Adjustment Programme (SAP) (Kenny, 2019; Sanusi, 2004). Despite this shift, Nigeria's trade flow fluctuated, with a trade surplus of ₦2.937 billion recorded in 1986 but recurring trade deficits in 1998, 2015, 2016, and between 2019 and 2020 (CBN, 2020). The extent to which exchange rate changes have contributed to Nigeria's recent decline in trade flow remains uncertain.

Ultimately, understanding the extent to which exchange rate volatility influences exports is essential for shaping Nigeria's trade and monetary policies. This knowledge is particularly relevant given the global transition toward export-led growth strategies, which have the potential to transform both developing and developed economies. Against this backdrop, this study investigates the impact of exchange rate volatility on Nigeria's exports, contributing to the ongoing debate on the interplay between exchange rate dynamics and trade performance.

Statement of the Problem

Despite being endowed with abundant natural and human resources, Nigeria struggles to position itself as a leading exporter of diversified products in the global market as pointed out by Mesagan et al. (2021). Exchange rate volatility has hindered planning, increased costs for exporters, and discouraged investment in export-oriented sectors (Salik & Aras, 2022). The country's dependency on oil revenue exacerbates these challenges, leaving other sectors vulnerable to external shocks

(Lal et al., 2023). Understanding the dynamics of exchange rates and their impact on export competitiveness is essential to developing sustainable economic policies.

Research Questions

1. How does exchange rate affect Nigeria's export performance?
2. What is the relationship between inflation and export performance of Nigeria?
3. How does interest rate affect Nigeria's export performance?

Literature Review

Conceptual Framework

Exchange rate dynamics refer to changes in the value of a country's currency relative to others, influenced by factors such as inflation, interest rates, and trade balances (Isibor et al., 2022). Export competitiveness involves a country's ability to produce goods and services that meet international quality and pricing standards (Arize et al., 2021). The nexus between these concepts highlights the impact of exchange rate stability on exporters' ability to penetrate global markets effectively.

The relationship between exchange rate volatility and exports spans diverse data sets and methodologies, yielding inconclusive findings. For instance, Altıntaş et al. (2011) employed multivariate cointegration and the Error Correction Model (ECM) using data from 1993Q3 to 2009Q4 to study Turkey's exports. Their results revealed a positive long-run impact of foreign income and exchange rate volatility on exports, while relative prices had a negative effect. In the short run, exchange rate volatility positively influenced exports, but relative prices exerted a negative impact.

Similarly, Oiro (2012) used the ARDL and GARCH methods to examine the effects of exchange rate volatility on Kenyan commodity exports (tea, horticulture, and coffee) to the EU and UK. Findings indicated a significant impact of volatility on specific commodities. In India, Srinivasan & Kalaivani (2013) applied ARDL to study the relationship between exchange rate volatility and real exports from 1970 to 2011, concluding that volatility negatively affected exports in both the short and long run.

Studies from other regions reflect similar diversity in findings. Chamunorwa & Choga (2015) used the GARCH method to analyze South Africa's export performance (2000–2014) and found a negative relationship with exchange rate volatility. Conversely, Yusoff & Sabit (2015) employed the Generalized Method of Moments (GMM) to examine ASEAN exports to China and found that exchange rate volatility negatively affected exports, while China's GDP positively influenced them.

Research in Jordan (Almohaisen, 2015), China (Shaikh & Hongbing, 2015), Indonesia (Safuan, 2017), and Vietnam (Thuy & Thuy, 2019) also produced mixed results. Across these studies, exchange rate volatility had varying impacts on exports, often conditioned by specific contexts, methodologies, and economic structures.

In Nigeria, studies have focused on both oil and non-oil exports with mixed conclusions. For example, Oyovwi & Ukavwe (2013) found a positive but insignificant effect of exchange rate volatility on imports and a significant positive effect on exports. Similarly, Adaramola (2016) identified a positive and significant relationship between exchange rate volatility and trade volumes. However, other studies, such as Yakub et al. (2019), reported a negative short-run impact on trade flows without significant long-run effects.

Theoretical Framework

1. **Purchasing Power Parity (PPP):** This theory posits that exchange rates should adjust to equalize the price levels of goods and services between countries, thus impacting trade balances (Ewubare & Ushie, 2022).
2. **Marshall-Lerner Condition:** It suggests that currency depreciation improves a country's trade balance if the sum of the price elasticities of exports and imports exceeds one (Muoneke et al., 2023).
3. **Balance of Payments Theory:** This framework explains how exchange rates adjust to ensure equilibrium in a country's balance of payments, reflecting the relationship between exports, imports, and capital flows (Shuabiu et al., 2021).

Theoretical perspectives also diverge. Traditional theories suggest that exchange rate volatility reduces exports by increasing profit uncertainty, while risk portfolio theories argue that the effects depend on income and substitution dynamics. Political economy theories, on the other hand, propose no clear link between exchange rate volatility and exports (Duru et al., 2022).

Empirical Literature

Ewubare & Ushie (2022) investigated the relationship between exchange rates and economic growth in Nigeria from 1981 to 2020. The study focused on the effects of exchange rates, inflation, and interest rates on gross domestic product (GDP). Data were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin and World Development Indicators. The analysis employed descriptive statistics, unit root tests, bounds cointegration tests, and the ARDL model. The unit root test results revealed mixed integration among the variables, with inflation stationary at levels and other variables stationary at first difference. The bounds cointegration test confirmed the existence of a long-run relationship between GDP growth and the explanatory variables. The findings indicated that exchange rates and inflation negatively impacted economic growth, suggesting that increases in these variables are detrimental to Nigeria's economic performance. Conversely, the study found a significant positive effect of interest rates on GDP growth, reflecting a scenario where businesses and households in Nigeria continue borrowing despite rising interest rates, often at the expense of product quality or by transferring costs to consumers. The study recommended that the federal government, through the CBN, should implement consistent exchange rate policies to promote a realistic and stable exchange rate capable of fostering economic growth in Nigeria.

Muoneke et al. (2023) explored the effects of extreme exchange rate fluctuations—both extremely small and extremely large—on the export trade of selected oil-exporting African countries from 1981Q1 to 2020Q4. The study highlighted the limitations of the standard non-linear ARDL model, citing inconsistencies in estimates, unreliable diagnostic tests, and an inability to account for extreme exchange rate variations. Instead, the study employed a multiple asymmetric threshold non-linear ARDL model, which proved more robust. The results revealed a long-run asymmetry between exchange rate variations and exports for most countries, with the exception of Nigeria, where symmetry was observed. Additionally, short-run asymmetry was evident across all the countries analyzed. The parameter estimates showed that the effects of extremely large exchange rate changes (major and minor appreciation/depreciation) significantly differed from those of extremely small changes, reflecting the exchange rate practices unique to each country. However, in the short run, the effects varied inconsistently across quantiles. Notably, Algeria was unaffected by major or minor exchange rate variations across all positive and negative shock quantiles. The study concluded with policy recommendations tailored to the specific conditions of the selected countries.

Shuabiu et al. (2021) examined how Global Value Chains (GVCs) influence the global economy, including international trade, GDP, and employment, particularly in sectors like commodities, electronics, and business service outsourcing. The study analyzed the interplay among competitively valued exchange rates, price levels, and economic growth in the Turkish economy, with a focus on insights from GVCs. Using annual data from 1980 to 2020, the researchers applied the ARDL bound test, Bayer and Hanck Cointegration (BHC) test, and ECM framework. The findings revealed that real effective exchange rates, exports, and imports significantly enhance economic performance and external trade competitiveness, especially within GVCs, in both the short and long run. The study recommended annual policies fostering a 10% equilibrium convergence to reduce reliance on foreign value-added inputs and emphasized importing only high-quality inputs for value addition in exports. It also called for further investigation into the nexus of monetary policy, GVCs, and economic growth.

Nnoli et al. (2023) investigated the impact of inflation and exchange rate on agricultural exports in Nigeria from 1986 to 2019 using 34 annual observations. Data were sourced from the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) Statistical Bulletin, FAOSTAT, and the World Development Indicator (WDI). The study employed Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF), Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root tests, Granger causality test, and the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique. Results showed unidirectional causality from agricultural export value (AEV) to the inflation rate (INF) and from the exchange rate (EXR) to the inflation rate. Additionally, the exchange rate (coefficient = 1057.724) positively and significantly impacted agricultural export value, while inflation rate (coefficient = 3661.635) also had a positive significant effect on AEV. The study recommended implementing a policy mix to stabilize and improve the value of the naira, thereby enhancing agricultural export value.

Olasehinde-Williams & Oshodi (2021) investigated the role of economic complexity in shaping export competitiveness among Africa's top 10 exporting countries, which collectively account for

approximately 78% of the continent's total trade volume. Using data from 2000 to 2018, the study employed both a parametric common correlated effects mean group estimation technique and a non-parametric time-varying model with fixed effects. The findings revealed that economic complexity significantly influences export competitiveness, though its impact is less pronounced compared to GDP, real exchange rates, trade openness, and foreign direct investment (FDI). The study concluded that while policies promoting economic complexity are important, they should not operate in isolation. Instead, governments should implement comprehensive trade policy reforms that integrate economic complexity alongside other critical factors like exchange rates, economic growth, trade openness, and FDI to maximize export performance.

Iheanachor & Ozegbe (2021) examined the impact of persistent exchange rate fluctuations on Nigeria's economic performance from 1986 to 2019. Motivated by the limited success of monetary policies aimed at achieving economic stability, the study employed the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) technique to assess both short-run and long-run effects. The findings revealed that exchange rate fluctuations, net foreign direct investment, and inflation exert significant adverse impacts on Nigeria's economic growth in the long run. This indicates that excessive exchange rate volatility is detrimental to economic performance. The study recommended export diversification through agriculture and agro-investment and urged the government to implement credible reforms in the foreign exchange system to mitigate the negative effects of exchange rate instability.

Comfort (2021) investigated the relationship between exchange rate volatility and economic growth in Nigeria from 1986 to 2019 using a Vector Error Correction Mechanism (VECM). The study found that exchange rate volatility positively influences inflation, unemployment, and the balance of trade but negatively affects economic growth and investment. Based on these results, it was recommended that policymakers avoid systematic currency devaluations to maintain exchange rate volatility at manageable levels, facilitating balance of payments adjustments without harming economic growth.

Ekanayake & Dissanayake (2022) analyzed the effects of real exchange rate volatility on the United States' exports to BRICS countries (Brazil, Russia, India, China, and South Africa) using quarterly data from 1993Q1 to 2021Q2. Focusing on the top 20 export products, the study employed Panel Least Squares, Panel Fully Modified Least Squares (FMOLS), Panel Dynamic Least Squares (DOLS), and the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) approach to cointegration analysis. The findings showed that foreign economic activity positively impacts exports, while real exchange rate and its volatility negatively affect exports in the long run across all five countries. However, the short-run effects of exchange rate volatility yielded mixed results, varying by the measure of volatility used.

Obomeghie & Ugbomhe (2021) investigated the impact of globalization on Nigeria's economic competitiveness, focusing on the country's ability to compete with developed nations in the global economy. Using the Least Squares method and data from 2006 to 2017, analyzed with Microfit 5.1 software, the study revealed a negative relationship between globalization and Nigeria's competitiveness. It highlighted that globalization has led to a decline in manufacturing industries, reducing their ability to compete with imported products. The study concluded that Nigeria's

innovation strategies are inadequate compared to those of developed nations, emphasizing the need for dynamic reforms to maximize the benefits of globalization and improve economic competitiveness.

Sambo et al. (2021) explored the relationship between real exchange rate volatility, trade balance, and financial development in Nigeria from 1980 to 2019, employing threshold autoregressive non-linear cointegration and non-linear ARDL techniques. The findings indicated that financial development amplifies the positive effects of exchange rate volatility on foreign trade. However, uncertainty in foreign capital flows negatively impacts international trade. The study recommended strengthening Nigeria's financial sector to mitigate credit market inefficiencies and support economic diversification and growth.

Mesagan et al. (2022) analyzed exchange rate asymmetries on trade and output growth across eight major African economies (1970–2019) using the NARDL framework. Results confirmed a long-run relationship between exchange rate, trade, and output growth. Currency depreciation positively influenced short-run growth but reduced long-run trade balances for most countries. Conversely, currency appreciation often negatively impacted both growth and trade. The study emphasized the need for context-specific exchange rate policies to stabilize trade and promote economic growth.

Uche & Nwamiri (2022) examined the asymmetric pass-through effects of exchange rate fluctuations on output growth in Nigeria using the NARDL model with monthly data from 2000M1 to 2018M12. The findings revealed that exchange rate depreciation retards output in the short run, with no significant long-run impact from either appreciation or depreciation. This indicates a misalignment between exchange rate movements and productivity in Nigeria. The study recommended aligning the naira-dollar exchange rate to enhance economic productivity.

Arize et al. (2021) provided the first application of the NARDL technique to analyze Thailand's export demand, assessing the effects of foreign economic activity, relative export prices, and exchange-rate risks. Results showed nonlinear and asymmetric cointegration, with exchange rate risks negatively affecting export volumes in both the long and short run. The study emphasized the importance of managing exchange-rate risks to sustain export performance.

Empirical evidences stress that the relationship between exchange rate volatility and exports is highly context-dependent, influenced by factors such as risk aversion, hedging opportunities, market structures, and currency contracts. Most recent studies tend to indicate a negative relationship, though no universal conclusion exists. This study seeks to address existing gaps by employing advanced econometric techniques, including ARDL-ECM model, to better understand the impact of exchange rate dynamics on exports, particularly within the Nigerian context.

Research Methodology

Research Design

The research design adopted for the study is based on the quasi-experimental research design. This design was informed due to the nature of data involved, which is a time series data.

Data Source

The data used for this study were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin. The period covered by the study is 1990-2023. It is worthy of mention that there is no economic reason for the choice of period; but the availability of data informed the period covered.

Model Specification

The functional form of the model is stated below:

$$EXP = f(EXR_t, INF_t, INT_t)$$

The econometric estimation form of the functional specification of the model above is presented as follows:

$$EXP = \beta + \beta_1 EXR + \beta_2 INF + \beta_3 INT + \mu$$

The Logged Form:

$$\text{Log}EXP = \beta + \beta_1 \text{log}EXR - \beta_2 \text{log}INF - \beta_3 \text{log}INT + \mu$$

Where:

EXP = Value of total exportation

EXR = Exchange rate

INF = Inflation rate

INT = Interest rate

u_t = Stochastic Term

A priori expectation = $\beta_1 > 0, \beta_2 > 0, \beta_3 > 0$.

Data Analysis Technique

Pre-Estimation Tests

The pre-estimation tests included descriptive analysis, stationarity tests using the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) method, and a bounds test for cointegration. These tests were conducted to ensure the suitability of the data for analysis. The stationarity tests determined the appropriate cointegration technique, while the cointegration tests assessed the existence of long-run relationships among the time series variables in the model. The choice of model estimation technique was based on the outcomes of these tests.

Model Estimation

The study employed both the Error Correction Model (ECM) and the Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) technique. The ARDL approach was applied when the variables exhibited a mixed

order of integration. For cointegrated variables Y_t and X_t , the ECM captures both short-run and long-run dynamics. In this model, b_1 represents the short-run effect, indicating the immediate impact of changes in X_t on Y_t , while π reflects the adjustment effect, showing the extent to which disequilibrium from the previous period influences adjustments in Y_t (Neusser, 2016).

The ARDL model, based on ordinary least squares (OLS), is applicable to both non-stationary time series and series with mixed integration orders. The long-run equation for the selected ARDL (kk) model is expressed as:

$$Y_t = \alpha + \sum_{i=1}^k \beta_i X_{t-i} + \epsilon_t$$

where X_{t-i} represents the explanatory variables or long-run variables, and k is the optimal lag order. The model's estimates are further refined using the associated ECM (Nkoro & Uko, 2016).

Post-Estimation Diagnostic Tests

The study conducted two key post-estimation diagnostic tests:

1. Serial Autocorrelation Test: This tested for the presence of autocorrelation among the residuals.
2. Heteroscedasticity Test: This evaluated whether the variance of the regression errors remained constant over time. A non-constant variance could result in high standard errors and reduce the reliability of the analytical results.

Additionally, the CUSUM test was applied to assess the stability of the estimated model, while the Granger causality test examined the causal relationships between the variables.

All analyses were performed using EViews version 10.

Results and Data Analysis

Descriptive Analysis

	LOG_EXP_	LOG_EXR_	LOG_INF_	LOG_INT_
Mean	3.924431	12.46488	3.854477	3.896178
Median	3.981549	12.37879	3.815204	3.858538
Maximum	3.101199	12.86190	3.985069	4.033525
Minimum	3.666122	12.20126	3.793352	3.848593
Std. Dev.	0.137826	0.241162	0.065262	0.057048
Skewness	-0.433330	0.448455	0.748228	0.927458
Kurtosis	2.564374	1.564488	2.006427	2.306197
Jarque-Bera	1.562092	4.655858	5.404447	6.373371
Probability	0.157117	0.007497	0.067056	0.141309
Sum	154.7766	486.1304	150.3246	151.9509
Sum Sq. Dev.	0.723353	2.210042	0.163346	0.123670
Observations	33	33	33	33

Descriptive statistics are essential tools in economic research, providing quick insights into the nature of the dataset. In the analysis presented, the researcher evaluated the skewness, kurtosis, and Jarque-Bera (JB) statistics to assess whether the variables follow a normal distribution.

Received: 02 January 2025

Revised: 09 January 2025

Accepted: 14 January 2025

Copyright © authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.14645025>

According to the JB test results, the inflation and exchange rate variables deviate from normality, as indicated by their probability values (Prob < 0.05). Conversely, the other variables exhibit normal distribution characteristics, with JB probability values exceeding the 0.05 threshold.

Unit Root: ADF Tests

Test at levels	Variables	P - Value	Comments
	LOGEXP	0.1127	Not stationary
	LOGEXR	0.9609	Not stationary
	LOGINF	0.0008	stationary
	LOGINT	0.6533	Not stationary
Test at First Difference	Variables	P-Value	Order of Integration
	LOGEXR	0.0238	I(1)
	LOGEXP	0.0052	I(1)
	LOGINT	0.0062	I(1)

Source: Authors computation using Eviews

The unit root test results are shown in the table shows that the variables are stationary at various levels. However, LOGINF is stationary at levels. The mixture of the variables in the ADF analysis satisfies for the use of ARDL model in the regression analysis.

Bounds Test for Cointegration

F-Bounds Test		Null Hypothesis: No levels relationship		
Test Statistic	Value	Signif.	I(0)	I(1)
			Asymptotic: n=1000	
F-statistic	5.833508	10%	2.75	3.79
k	5	5%	3.12	4.25
		2.5%	3.49	4.67
		1%	3.93	5.23

Source: Authors computation from Eviews

Based on the results of the stationarity test, the study determined that the variables in the specified model exhibit different orders of integration, indicating a mixed order of integration. Consequently, the ARDL Bounds Cointegration test was employed to examine the presence of a long-term relationship between the variables. The test results confirm the existence of a long-run relationship between the dependent and independent variables over the study period.

The ARDL approach offers several advantages. As highlighted by Ibukun & Aremo (2017), its primary strength lies in its suitability for small sample sizes. Unlike other cointegration methods that require separate estimations of long-run relationships through multiple equations, the ARDL model simplifies the process by using a single reduced-form equation (Pesaran & Shin, 1995).

ARDL Model Estimation

LONG RUN RESULTS

Dependent: LOGEXP

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
@TREND	0.016594	0.006962	2.383321	0.0254
LOG_EXP_(-1)*	-0.578051	0.203848	-2.835691	0.0091
LOG_INT_**	-0.065679	0.128858	-0.509702	0.6149
LOG_INF_**	5.334369	3.162590	1.686709	0.1046
LOG_EXR_**	-5.834198	3.381586	-1.725285	0.0973

Dependent: LOGEXP

SHORT RUN RESULT

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
LOG_EXR_	-0.265679	0.128858	-2.061797	0.0009
LOG_INF_	-1.004369	0.162590	-6.177311	0.0000
LOG_INT_	-3.356198	1.381586	-2.429257	0.0073
CointEq(-1)*	-0.615251	0.136447	4.236441	0.0003
R-Squared =0.705612	F-Stat = 9.896152	Prob(F-stat) 0.000529	D-W stat=2.193392	

The results above present both the longrun and shortrun tests results of the ARDL model. The coefficient of determination, which tests the goodness-of-fit, shows that the independent variables explain the changes in the dependent variable at 71%. The F-test, which tests for the overall significance of the model, is also statistically significant while the speed of adjustment between the shortrun and the longrun is 0.61 (61%) annually.

Serial Autocorrelation Test

Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

F-statistic	0.233389	Prob. F(2,22)	0.3275
Obs*R-squared	3.576331	Prob. Chi-Square(2)	0.1226

Source: Author's computation from Eviews

The serial or autocorrelation helps to determine if the variables are serially correlated or not. As the result shows using the Prob of F-stat (0.3275), there is no problem of serial autocorrelation.

Heteroskedasticity Test

Heteroskedasticity Test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	5.711465	Prob. F(7,24)	0.6270
Obs*R-squared	23.00632	Prob. Chi-Square(7)	0.3317
Scaled explained SS	32.55961	Prob. Chi-Square(7)	0.1270

Source: Author's computation from Eviews

The variance of the model is also constant based on the results of the heteroskedasticity test.

Granger Causality Test

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Date: 12/15/24 Time: 19:41

Sample: 1992 2020

Lags: 2

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
LOG_EXR_ does not Granger Cause LOG_EXP_ LOG_EXP_ does not Granger Cause LOG_EXR_	37	1.08333 0.83243	0.3506 0.4442
LOG_INF_ does not Granger Cause LOG_EXP_ LOG_EXP_ does not Granger Cause LOG_INF_	37	1.60697 54.6364	0.2163 5.E-11
LOG_INT_ does not Granger Cause LOG_EXP_ LOG_EXP_ does not Granger Cause LOG_INT_	37	1.74407 54.8089	0.1910 5.E-11

Source: Author's computation from Eviews

The pair-wise granger causality test shows the direction of cause between the dependent and the independent variables. This does not necessarily connote a relationship between the variables. As shown above, there is a bidirectional causality between the EXP and INF, and INT. However, there is no causality between EXP and EXR over the period.

CUSUM Test

The CUSUM Test shows that the model is well specified.

Tests of Hypotheses

H₀₁: *there is no significant relationship between EXR and EXP in Nigeria.*

The result shows that there is a negative relationship between EXP and EXR as unexpected apriori. As EXR increases by a unit, EXP decreases by -0.265679 and vice versa. Again, EXR is statistically significant at 5% level of significance based on the t-test. We will therefore accept the alternative hypothesis, reject the null and conclude that there is a significant relationship between EXP and EXR over the period.

H₀₂: *there is no significant relationship between INF and EXP in Nigeria.*

Further, the result shows that there is a negative relationship between EXP and INF as also expected apriori. As INF increases by a unit, EXP decreases by -1.004369 and vice versa. Again, INF is statistically significant at 5% level of significance. We will therefore accept the alternative hypothesis, reject the null and conclude that there is a significant relationship between EXP and INF over the period.

H₀₃: *there is no significant relationship between INT and EXP in Nigeria.*

Moreover, the result shows that there is a negative relationship between EXP and INT as expected apriori. As INT increases by a unit, EXP increases by -3.356198 and vice versa. Again, INT is statistically significant at 5% level of significance. We will therefore accept the alternative hypothesis, reject the null and conclude that there is a significant relationship between EXP and INT over the period.

Discussion of the Findings

We could glean from the results above the extent to which the independent variables affected the dependent variable over the period. Any increase in the independent variables will lead to a decrease in the dependent variable and vice versa. It is clear from the results that exchange rate dynamics and other key, related variables negatively affect export of the country. An increment in exchange rate, ceteris paribus, there is supposed to be an increase in exportation of goods and vice versa. Unfortunately, results from the data analysis shows that there is the exchange rate has negative but significant effect on Nigeria's exportation value, thus, making the country very uncompetitive in the global market. A key reason for this is the lack of exportable products as highlighted by Ewubare & Ushie (2022). While there are so many issues bedeviling the economy, making it difficult to build up exportable products in Nigeria's export basket, a key issue is the lack of political will by the major political players to see the success of the project called "Nigeria" (Nnoli et al., 2022).

Again, the study found a negative and significant relationship between exportation and interest rate, indicating the negative effect increasing interest rate can have on the export base of the country. The result is the inability of the country to compete with other countries globally due to limited or lack of exportable products. As Ekanayake & Dissanayake (2022) found in their study, few exportable products make the country weak in the international market. They are susceptible to price changes and national policy changes of the importing countries. For instance, a change in the importation of a particular product will negatively affect the exporting country. The findings of this study agree with the findings of Sambo et al. (2021) and Mesagan et al. (2022) who noted that interest rate has a negative relationship with the balance of trade of Nigeria.

Finally, the study found a negative and significant relationship between exportation and inflation rate. With the increase in INF, EXP decreases also and vice versa, implying that with an increase in inflation, businesses will find it more difficult keeping their operations on, indirectly affecting the quantity and quality of goods they can export. Inflation makes country's exportable goods less competitive as the goods will be of less quality in many cases as compared to other countries goods. This finding agrees with the findings of Afolabi (2022) who also highlighted the importance of controlling inflation to improve the chances of a country being competitive.

Conclusion and Recommendations

Exchange rate dynamics remain a critical determinant of Nigeria's competitiveness in the global market. While the naira's volatility and structural challenges have constrained the country's trade performance and economic growth, targeted reforms can unlock Nigeria's potential and enhance its position in the global economy (Orji et al., 2021). A holistic approach that addresses both macroeconomic and structural factors is essential for achieving exchange rate stability, promoting economic diversification, and fostering sustainable growth (Uche & Nwamiri, 2022).

The findings underscore the importance of aligning monetary and fiscal policies, investing in infrastructure and human capital, and promoting institutional reforms. Specifically, there is need to ensure that inflation, interest rate, and exchange rates are harmonized to improve the competitiveness of the country. Aside expanding the export basket of the country, there is need to also improve on the goods exported, making them command more value in the international market. By addressing these areas, Nigeria can reduce its reliance on oil revenues, strengthen its non-oil

export base, and enhance its resilience to external shocks. Ultimately, improving exchange rate management and competitiveness requires a long-term commitment to policy coherence, structural transformation, and economic diversification. Such efforts will position Nigeria as a formidable player in the global economy, capable of leveraging its resources and talents for sustainable development.

The study therefore, recommends that the fiscal policies bothering on interest rate, inflation rate be amended to accommodate small scale manufacturers, giving them the opportunity to export more of their products. The immediate result will be an increase in the GDP while the remote result will be a general increase in the welfare of the people. Importantly, the financial authorities must device means of stabilizing the exchange rate. The instability of Naira has resulted to the inability of the country to compete with other countries of the same caliber in the global market.

References

- Afolabi, J. (2022). Financial development, trade openness, and economic growth in Nigeria. *Iranian Economic Review*, 26(1), 237-254.
- Arize, A. C., Ogunc, A., Kalu, E. U., & Malindretos, J. (2021). New evidence on exchange-rate volatility and export flows in Thailand: nonlinearity and asymmetric ARDL investigation. *The International Trade Journal*, 35(2), 194-218.
- Audi, M. (2024). The impact of exchange rate volatility on long-term economic growth: Insights from Lebanon.
- Comfort, A. B. (2021). The impact of exchange rate volatility on economic growth in Nigeria: A dynamic econometric approach. *African Journal of Business and Economic Development* | ISSN, 2782, 7658.
- Dehalwar, K., & Sharma, S. N. (2023). *Fundamentals of Research Writing and Uses of Research Methodologies*. Edupedia Publications Pvt Ltd.
- Duru, I. U., Eze, M. A., Saleh, A. S., Yusuf, A., & Uzoma, K. (2022). Exchange rate and trade balance in Nigeria: testing for the validity of J-curve phenomenon and Marshall-Lerner condition. *Asian Themes in Social Sciences Research*, 6(1), 1-11.
- Ekanayake, E. M., & Dissanayake, A. (2022). Effects of real exchange rate volatility on trade: Empirical analysis of the United States exports to BRICS. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 15(2), 73.
- Ewubare, D. B., & Ushie, U. A. (2022). Exchange rate fluctuations and economic growth in Nigeria (1981-2020). *International Journal of Development and Economic Sustainability*, 10(1), 41-55.
- Iheanachor, N., & Ozegbe, A. E. (2021). The consequences of exchange rate fluctuations on Nigeria's economic performance: An autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL)

- approach. *International Journal of Management, Economics and Social Sciences (IJMESS)*, 10(2-3), 68-87.
- Isibor, A. A., Kehinde, A. A., Felicia, O. O., Tolulope, A. F., Victoria, A. A., & Mercy, U. E. (2022). Achieving sustained performance in the Nigerian oil and gas sector despite exchange rate fluctuations: A VAR Approach. *International Journal of Energy Economics and Policy*, 12(3), 341-351.
- Lal, M., Kumar, S., Pandey, D. K., Rai, V. K., & Lim, W. M. (2023). Exchange rate volatility and international trade. *Journal of Business Research*, 167, 114156.
- Mesagan, E. P., Alimi, O. Y., & Vo, X. V. (2022). The asymmetric effects of exchange rate on trade balance and output growth. *The Journal of Economic Asymmetries*, 26, e00272.
- Mesagan, E. P., Kushimo, K., & Umar, D. I. (2021). Do fluctuations in exchange rate hinder non-oil export? An analysis of agriculture and manufacturing in Nigeria. *SN Business & Economics*, 1, 1-23.
- Muoneke, O. B., Okere, K. I., & Onuoha, F. C. (2023). Extreme exchange rate dynamics and export trade in the selected oil-exporting countries in Africa. Multiple asymmetric threshold non-linear ARDL approach. *The Journal of International Trade & Economic Development*, 32(6), 854-877.
- Nnoli, T. I., Enilolobo, S. O., Hassan, C. O., & Bello, A. B. (2023). Inflation, exchange rate and agricultural export in Nigeria. *Greener Journal of Agricultural Sciences*, 13(2), 91-98.
- Obomeghie, M. A., & Ugbohmhe, U. O. (2021). Globalization and its brunt on nigeria global economic competitiveness: the need for holistic and dynamic strategies. *Innovation Journal of Social Sciences and Economic Review*, 3(1), 1-06.
- Olasehinde-Williams, G., & Oshodi, A. F. (2021). Can Africa raise export competitiveness through economic complexity? Evidence from (non)-parametric panel techniques. *African Development Review*, 33(3), 426-438.
- Orji, A., Abubakar, M., Ogbuabor, J. E., Anthony-Orji, O. I., & Ojonta, O. I. (2021). Non-oil export and exchange rate nexus in Nigeria: Another empirical verification. *Growth*, 8(1), 39-47.
- Osazevbaru, H. O. (2021). Interest rate and exchange rate volatility and the performance of the Nigerian informal sector: Evidence from small and medium-sized enterprises. *Ekonomski horizonti*, 23(1), 19-32.
- Salik, A. M., & Aras, O. N. (2022). The effects of trade openness, foreign direct investment and exchange rate fluctuations on non-oil gross domestic product growth in Nigeria. *Journal of Management, Economics, and Industrial Organization*, 6(1), 98-117.

- Sambo, N. U., Farouq, I. S., Isma'il, M. T., Sambo, N. U., Farouq, I. S., & Isma'il, M. T. (2021). Asymmetric effect of exchange rate volatility on trade balance in Nigeria. *National Accounting Review*, 3(3), 342-359.
- Shuabiu, U. A., Usman, M. A., & Çavuşoğlu, B. (2021). The Nexus among Competitively Valued Exchange Rates, Price Level, and Growth Performance in the Turkish Economy; New Insight from the Global Value Chains. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 14(11), 528.
- Uche, E., & Nwamiri, S. I. (2022). Dynamic effects of exchange rate movements on productivity levels: New evidence from Nigeria based on NARDL. *Journal of Development Policy and Practice*, 7(1), 96-111.